

DIARY OF A BUTTERFLY: A DIRECTING DEBUT

by

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8070900

A Project Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the
Requirements to Graduate with University Honors

The University Honors Program
California State University, Fullerton
May 2023

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Date:

5/25/23

5/19/23

Introduction

I began writing poetry in 2019. It became my favorite outlet for expressing the complex emotions I was experiencing. I then decided I wanted to share my art with the world. Thus, *Diaries of a Butterfly*, my poetry project, was born. Combining my passions for aesthetic visuals and creative writing, I took photos and videos of inspiring sights I would stumble upon in my life, and accompanied those images with my written words. However, I yearn to take my work to the next level. The solution to my creative problem: to marry my words to film.

With the help of fellow student filmmakers, I sought a way to marry the poetry that I had been writing for the past three years to moving pictures, an undertaking I had long awaited to embark on. We succeeded. I present to you, my first-ever short films: *Where the Butterflies Once Danced* and *More*. I hope that through my art you can find the pieces of you that are missing, or you pick the pieces of yourself that you want to put into our world. To find, a deeper connection to our world, but also, to yourself, and to keep exploring through art. There is so much out there.

Materials and Methods

At the beginning of the creative process for my short films, my mentor wanted to first equip me with the basic technical knowledge of filmmaking. This was my first time ever directing or writing for film and I had a few things I needed to learn.

One of the first aspects I learned about filmmaking was the five-step production process. These five stages include development, preproduction, production, post-production, and distribution. I decided to follow this process for my honors project.

My mentor also sent me videos and gave me advice on the technicalities of filmmaking. Videos from Studio Binder were crucial learning materials that I will visit again in the future. It was through these I learned the basics of cinematography.

After completing the scripts and storyboards for both of my short films, it was time to figure out all of the other elements. This included finding locations, and costumes, casting other actors if needed, and finding my crews.

I began placing these elements together for *Where the Butterflies Once Danced* back in January. I secured fellow CSUF film student Aidan Shon as my primary director of photography, and CSULB film alumni Louis Huyn as my secondary. This short film ultimately ended up with six directors of photography.

For this short film, I needed someone to play my romantic lead costar. I was able to secure my friend CSUF theatre alumni Avi Spitzer to fill this role. For costumes, we both used what was in our closets. I planned and coordinated every costume needed by scene.

Locations were the trickiest element of production for this project. I wanted to capture the feel of a specific small mountain town in Tehachapi, California. We did as much filming as we could there despite working with everyone's schedules and the fact that it was about two and a half

hours away. Some sequences were also shot in Yorba Linda, California. As for equipment, this first short film was mostly shot on a Canon eos m50.

The production for *More*, my second short film, was far less complicated, yet still just as important. I was able to find a director of photography in my youngest sister Priscilla Werre. Luckily I did not have to worry about casting for this one because I was the only one acting in it. I found my outfit in my closet once again. For my location, I utilized one of the bathrooms on the first floor of the humanities building on campus.

Results

By the time the conference came, I had just entered the post-production phase of editing my short films. I did not make it all the way through to the last and final phase of the distribution as I originally intended. However, I was able to show early draft versions of both short films for everyone to see at the conference. I did not get to have the amount of time that I desired to have for editing due to the long production phase for *Where the Butterflies Once Danced*. However, I am proud of my work and where the short films are now. My mentor and I came up with a plan to continue to help critique my editing over the summer. My goal is to get both of them to a place where I can submit them to film festivals and then, my poetry youtube channel.

Discussion

What my results mean to me is that the process of making a film is endlessly complex, strenuous, and layered. You must try to carefully schedule as much of your filmmaking process as you can, and you must try your hardest to meet your deadlines. However, you will always probably be behind that schedule. The process of filmmaking is also very drawn-out. You will never truly know how long it will take you to get a shot right. The director might make a change mid-shoot. An actor might do something the director likes and then the director might want to expand on that. The process of filmmaking gives a whole new meaning to the saying “You can’t rush perfection”. However, the reward is the birth of a brand-new world of places and characters that introduces people to your imagination; your vision. It is your place that you have carved out into the world for others to visit. It is your legacy of what is in your heart and mind. It is the stamp that you make on this world when you leave it behind. That is the reward of a lifetime.

Conclusions

I gathered invaluable lessons along the way during my journey in filmmaking. As the writer, director, main actress, and editor, some hats were more challenging to wear than others. Juggling all these roles (some at the same time) was difficult and yet, somehow, helpful at the same time. I would often have to switch between being an actress and a director back and forth during an entire shoot. Some days, it was hard to switch between being an actress and then a director and being able to give my all to both roles. On other days, in an interesting turn of events, the fact that I would have to juggle both would help me focus harder on being my best for both in a way that I would not have gotten just by focusing on one role.

Being a director was my most challenging experience yet. It tested my social skills and confidence in ways that I deeply appreciate. I learned how to work with other people's schedules and how to plan my set dates according to those schedules. I also honed my communication skills by learning how to tell directions to different people in different ways. Not everyone learns the same way and understands directions the same way. I had to learn how to adapt to different people's communication styles and learning styles and try to accommodate them. Another one of the most important lessons I learned from being a director was how to stand up for myself. I have always had trouble with conflict. I have always been afraid and even anxious about it. Now in my life, however, I find myself yearning to stop being a people pleaser and to stand up for what I want and what I believe instead. I am so used to letting my needs and my vision go unnoticed, and now, as a director, your job is to make others cooperate to make your vision come to life. I needed to learn how to work with and manage other people's personalities, no matter how difficult, in order to make them agree to come together to help me with this project. Luckily, I

did not run into any difficult people to work with on either project. But, I must continue to get over my fears of confrontation and not allow myself to become intimidated by others.

I am grateful for the director I have become while working on these projects, and I hope to continue to evolve into the director I need to be for my future film projects. As a director, I am a hype woman who tries to get her happy, bubbly, and jokey, yet determined and focused-when-needed energy to rub off on her cast and crew. I try to be extremely grateful and caring and I try to express this through words as much as I can after every wrap. I cannot wait to see how I will grow and change in being a director.